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VIRTUAL GALLERY: A NEXUS OF ARTISTIC PRACTICE AND RESEARCH

(Poster abstract)

This poster demonstrates the convergence of art, research methods and technological innovation within the digital humanities, specifically through the roles of artist-researchers and art anthropologists at the virtual Blue Point Art Gallery London. Created in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, this small but dynamic platform uses interactive 3D graphics accessible through web browsers to create a multifaceted space for creative expression, documentation and education. The gallery encourages both verbal and non-verbal interactions between artists, researchers and the public, with exhibitions delivered via WebGL and accessible directly on internet-connected devices without the need for additional installations.

An exemplary project is 'The Dystopia of Imitation', supported by Arts Council England. It features a transition from virtual installation to augmented reality (AR), starting with an animated 3D sculpture inspired by Johannes Vermeer's 'The Milkmaid'. This project illustrates the gallery's workflow by combining traditional sculptural techniques with digital methods, culminating in a generative art object in AR, signifying the merging of the physical and virtual realms. Such innovations demonstrate the potential of virtual galleries and AR to widen access to art, foster global collaboration and democratise the art process.

To further emphasise our interdisciplinary approach, the Gallery is also involved in educational collaborations. One notable project explores the reception of Stanisław Vincenz's work through a virtual exhibition of previously unknown photographs of the Hutsul region taken by Lidio Cipriani in 1933. These photographs, in the possession of Jacopo Moggi-Cecchi (University of Florence), have been digitised for this exhibition, which will be enhanced with additional multimedia elements and an accompanying bilingual book.

The Gallery also hosted a number of other exhibitions, including an exhibition of sketches by the Polish poet and artist Cyprian Norwid (along with an international conference and the development of a monograph). These projects underline the Gallery's commitment to non-commercial activities and its role as a nexus of artistic practice and research. They exemplify our commitment to integrating digital innovation into scholarly and artistic endeavours.

Blue Point Art Gallery is characterised by its fundamental research orientation and its focus on the digital value of design tasks. Our efforts extend beyond virtual exhibitions to include textual studies published as e-books and archived, for example, in the ZENODO repository.

In the context of gallery workflows, our approach integrates reproducible digital methods to standardise project management across artistic and academic collaborations. By using digital tools such as standardised digital archiving protocols, we can ensure consistency and high fidelity in the reproduction of results across different projects. For example, the transformation of The Milkmaid sculpture into AR can serve as a template for subsequent digital art transformations, using scripted automation to replicate and adapt the workflow for future exhibitions. This systematic application increases the scalability and applicability of our methods, enabling broader, more collaborative projects that maintain rigorous academic and artistic standards.

These initiatives highlight the Gallery's unique position within the digital humanities, combining artistic exploration with rigorous academic research to foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of art across global and digital landscapes.

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PHOTO DOCUMENTATION:

Figure 1. An exhibition of *Dystopia of imitation* in the Blue Point Art Gallery, <https://dystopiaofimitation.bluepointart.uk/>

Figure 2. Steps to take a snapshot capturing the unique shape generated by the application.

Figure 3. The two parts of the pitcher cut by the model of spilt milk exist in two different realities.

Figure 4. An aerial view of the exhibition interiors, <https://vincenz.bluepointart.uk>.

Figure 5. An exhibition of photographs of the Hutsul region by Lidio Cipriani (1933).

Figure 6. An exhibition of sketches by Cyprian Norwid (1838-1863), <https://norwid.szkiec.bluepointart.uk/>.

Figure 7. A close-up of one of the Norwid's works.